

Review Article

Prevalence and Management of HIV infection on infants from HIV-infected mother: A review

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Abstract

Background: The prevalence of HIV infection in infants born to HIV-infected mothers is a pressing global health issue. The World Health Organization estimates that in 2018, 570,000 children under age 15 were newly infected with HIV, and the majority of those infections were attributed to mother to child transmission of the virus. HIV infection in infants born to HIV-infected mothers can have devastating and long-lasting effects on an affected child's health as well as their psychological, social, and economic wellbeing.

Methodology: This paper reviewed the current scientific literature examining the prevalence of HIV infection on infants from HIV-infected mothers. We focused on factors associated with a reduction or increase in the prevalence of mother-to-child transmission of HIV, such as the use of antiretroviral drugs, interventions during labor and delivery, and breastfeeding methods. Additionally, we provided an overview of the psychological, social, and economic implications of HIV infection on infants from HIV-infected mothers. Finally, we discussed strategies on prevention, management, and treatment of mother-to-child transmission of HIV.

Conclusion: The findings of this paper underscore the importance of improving local health systems and prioritizing resources to search for effective interventions to prevent the prevalence of HIV infection on infants from HIV-infected mothers. This research is critical to reducing the global burden of mother-to-child transmission of HIV and creating health equality for all.

1. Introduction

HIV is classified into two primary types: type 1 (HIV-1) is the most frequent form, while type 2 (HIV-2) is primarily found in west Africa, with few cases being reported in Mozambique and Angola [1]. Dual infection with HIV-1 and HIV-2 is possible, though it has been proposed that HIV-2 infection may offer some protection against HIV-1 acquisition. While HIV-1 prevalence is rising in these areas, HIV-2 prevalence has stayed relatively stable, and the clinical course of HIV-2 disease is slower than that of HIV-1 [1].

There is evidence of HIV-2 transmission from mother to child, however it happens less frequently than HIV-1 [2]. This is the reason that HIV-1 is the primary focus of diagnostic methods for HIV in newborns. It is predicted that by 2010, in the most afflicted regions of the region, AIDS will raise baby morbidity by 25% and under-five mortality by over 100% if the spread of the virus is not controlled. As of today [3], 8.2 million children have lost both of their parents to AIDS; at least 95% of these individuals are African.

In several underdeveloped nations, HIV infection during pregnancy has emerged as the most prevalent pregnancy-related problem. An estimated 1.5 million HIV-positive women are expected to become pregnant each year, and over 1600 HIV-positive children will be infected every day through mother-to-child transmission [3, 4]. In areas where HIV prevalence is high, maternity services have a number of duties. The goals are as follows: first, to make testing available to women and help them use the results to maintain their health in the best possible way; second, to use the right kind of intervention to lower the rate of HIV transmission from mother to child (MTC); and third, to equip and train healthcare workers to prevent nosocomial HIV and other pathogen transmission [5].

In 2006, precisely in may, 2 days meeting hosted by the world health organization (WHO) and United state centre for disease control and prevention (CDC) resulted in a consensus statement on the use of the assay (DNA PCR method) Roche Amplicor for early infant diagnosis in the prevention of mother-to-infant transmission (PMTCT) program. Also consensus was reached on the use of direct blood spot (DBS) specimen from infant as a mean for ensuring greater accessibility to serologic and virology testing for pediatric HIV infection.

Targets for treatment of pediatric HIV are not being met in many African countries despite the availability of the appropriate drugs needed for anti retroviral therapy (ART). African children infected with HIV are dying at an alarming rate. A meta analysis published in 2004 showed that approximately 35% of infected children in African died before one year of age and more than 52% died before their 2nd birthday [6].

Data from Zambia showed that 30-50% of infected infants died by 2 years of age [7] and recently publishes studied from south African found that 40% of HIV affected infant died by 2 months of age [8]. The study explained that infant were lost at follow-up by 6 weeks and 85% by 12 months Age over a 24 months period. These results suggest that HIV-infected infant are not receiving timely access to Antiretroviral therapy (ART) because most do not present at mother to child health care (MCH) clinics and HIV infection is not detected in a timely manner.

2. Methodology

2.1. Epidemiology

HIV is transmitted in three ways; through unprotected sexual intercourse, heterosexual or homosexual; through blood or blood products, donated semen or organs; or from an infected mother to her child (vertical or mother-to-child transmission). More than 70% of infections are as a result of heterosexual transmission and over 90% of infection in children result from mother-to-child transmission [9]. Estimations of the regional distribution of HIV infection are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Regional estimate of people living with HIV/AIDS.

Region	Adults children living with HIV/AIDS	Adult prevalence rate	Percent of HIV-positive adults who are women	Cumulative no. of orphan
Sub-saharan African	22.5million	8.0%	50%	7.8 million
North frican & middle east	210,000	0.13%	20%	14,200
South & south-east Asia	6.7million	0.69%	25%	220,000
East Asia & pacific	560,000	0.068%	11%	1,900
Latin American	1.4million	0.57%	20%	91,000
Caribbean	330,000	1.96%	35%	48,000
Eastern Europe & central Asia	270,000	0.14%	20%	30
Weastern Europe	500,000	0.25%	20%	8,700
North America	890,000	0.56%	20%	70,000
Australia & New Zealand	12,000	0.1%	5%	300
Total	33.4 million	1.1%	43%	8.2 milliion

Although the HIV pandemic is centered in the developing world, Acquired immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) has also become a leading cause of death [10]. In developed countries, HIV seropositive women are more likely to be intravenous drug users, partner of drug users or bisexual men, or be involved in sex work [11]. American study has showed that 47% of mothers of HIV infected were intravenous drug users, and 22% reported sex with an intravenous drugs user [12].

The situation is quite different in developing countries, where heterosexual transmission is the predominant mode of spread. Southern African is the most affected region [4]. In Kenya, Malawi, Namibia, Rwanda, South African, Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe, over 10% of women attending antenatal clinic in urban areas are HIV- positive, with rates of almost 60% in some sites [3, 4].

Till date, African has been the centre of the epidemic but a rapid rise in infection rate has been seen in south east Asia. In Thailand, prevalence in women in antenatal clinic has risen from 0% in 1989 to 2.3% in1995 and continue to rise. Similar increase are reported from some indian cities, Latin American and Caribbean [3].

Although the prevalence rate in pregnant women has been considered a reliable indicator of the infection rate in populations [13]. According to a study conducted in Tanzania's Mwanza area, where the frequency of prenatal attendants was 0.75 lower than the general population, surveillance at antenatal clinics may be underestimating the population prevalence. This underestimation may be made worse by a decline in HIV-positive women's fertility, as reported in the Rakai district of Uganda, due to both subfertility and an increase in early pregnancy loss [14].

In urban Uganda there has been a reported decrease in the prevalence of HIV infection in pregnant women over the past few years. The 20% drop in prevalence is thought to be due to behavior change following aggressive AIDS education campaigns [15].

3. Susceptibility of Women To Hiv Infection

Women in the developing world are at higher risk of HIV than their male for a number of reasons, biological and sociological.

3.1. Biological Factors

The rate of transmission of HIV from male to female is two to three higher than that from female to male [16]. The Langerhans cells of the cervix may provide a portal of entry for HIV and it has been suggested that some HIV serotype may have higher affinity for these, and therefore to be more efficient in heterosexual transmission [17].

Vulval and vaginal inflammation or ulceration may facilitate entry of the virus. Sexually transmitted diseases (STD) are common in many African countries, where HIV prevalence is also high [18]. Inadequately treated or “silent” disease may be a major factor in facilitating HIV infection and Chlamydia infection and other sexually transmitted disease may act as co-factors for transmission [19].

Syphilis rate as high as 30% have been described in antenatal women and 4.2% of women in a population based study in Tanzania reported a history of genital ulceration [20], which has been well established as a co-factor for HIV acquisition [21]. In Zimbabwe, women reporting a history of genital ulceration and pelvic inflammatory disease were six more likely to be HIV-positive [22]. Improved STD treatment in a randomized controlled trial in Tanzania was shown to reduce the rate of new HIV infections. Other non-sexually transmitted cervical lesions, such as schistosomiasis, may also facilitate HIV infection [23]. Although the evidence is still inconclusive, associations between oral and injectable contraceptive use and increased HIV risk have been reported.

3.2. Socio-Cultural Factors

The settings in cultures and communities that deprive women of agency over their own bodies put them essentially at greater danger. Women have the combined burden of HIV infection and providing care for family members who are affected, and they are sometimes wrongly labelled as the source of the virus. Many women are forced into commercial sex labour in order to survive due to gender inequality, poverty, limited access to education, and a lack of economic prospects; these women are therefore at a higher risk of contracting HIV [24].

Conversely, many more women are monogamous, but are at high risk due to the sexual behaviors of their male partner. Traditional practices and customs such as “dry sex” practices, vaginal douching with non-antiseptics compounds, female circumcision and “widow cleansing” may all have an effect on increasing women’s risk of HIV infection [25].

Despite their high risk of infection, cultural practices and pressure often prevent women from taking the necessary precautions to guard against infection. Use of male condoms is low in many developing countries. The desire and the societal pressure to reproduce make it difficult for women to practice protected sex. Young women are at highest risk of infections in developing countries. Many of them at the beginning of their reproductive lives. Even after a diagnosis of HIV infection, most women will not change their reproductive choices [26].

3.3. Effect of Pregnancy on The Natural History

In pregnancy, immune function is suppressed in both HIV-infected and uninfected women [3]. There is a decrease in immunoglobulin, reduced complement levels in early pregnancy and a more significant decrease in cell-mediated immunity during pregnancy. These normal changes during pregnancy have led to concern that the effect of pregnancy in HIV disease could be to accelerate the progression of the infection.

African women do not appear to experience more rapid progression of HIV disease during their pregnancies, despite the additional factors of multiple pregnancies, other infections and poor nutrition. African research does not support the existence of a short-term synergistic effect on the immune system between pregnancy and HIV infection. In a Kenya study, the difference in the changes over pregnancy in CD4+ and CD8 cells and their ratio not statistically significant HIV-positive and negative women [27]. Percentage were shown to be stable in HIV sero-positive women in late pregnancy and the postpartum period in a Malawi study, demonstrating little effect of pregnancy on immune status [28].

3.4. Effect of HIV Infection on Pregnancy

HIV infection has been reported to have little effect on pregnancy outcome or complication in the developed world [27]. It is often difficult to determine the relative contribution of HIV infection, drug use and inadequate antenatal care to adverse outcome in these women. Adverse pregnancy outcome have, however been reported more commonly in a number of African studies [27] including complication of both early and late pregnancy. HIV may be the direct cause or a marker of a complex interaction of related medical and social conditions that affect pregnancy. Other studies have demonstrated no association [29]. These complication rate vary across studies and may reflect the extent of the epidemic and the nature of the HIV-related disease in different communities.

Complication of early pregnancy have been associated with HIV infection in several studies [27]. HIV-1 and HIV-2 infection in African have been linked to a higher rate of spontaneous abortion [2]. HIV seropositive women were 1.47 times more likely to have had a previous spontaneous abortion, and this rose to 1.81 in women in Uganda who were seropositive for both HIV and syphilis.

Syphilis is more common in HIV-positive women in African studies. Concurrent infection with syphilis was shown in 33% of HIV-positive pregnant women in South Africa: three times higher than the rate in HIV seronegative women. These high rate of syphilis may confound studies of pregnancy outcome unless the potential bias is taken into account in analysis. All HIV-positive pregnant women should be screened for syphilis, in low prevalence areas.

Preterm labour may be more common in HIV-positive women in some rate as high as double those rate seen in uninfected women in some reports [27]. Preterm rupture of membrane may also be increased in HIV-positive women and *abruption placentae* has been described as more common in HIV-positive women in South Africa and Kenya [30].

There is little difference in the birth weight of babies born to HIV-positive mother in developed countries [31]. In Edinburgh, HIV seropositivity was associated with a decrease in birth weight, but this was than the drop attributable to smoking. Low birth weight has been reported in some studies in developing countries. In a Nairobi study, HIV-positive women showed a threefold increase in the risk of delivering low birth weight baby [30] This risk was higher with symptom-tic HIV infection. In Zambia, the birth weight of babies born to HIV-positive mother were significantly lower than those of babies of seronegative women. In a prospective study in Rwanda, birth weight was significantly lower in singleton infants of asymptomatic women, although the difference in mean birth weight between the two group was only 120 g. Other studies in predominantly asymptomatic cohorts have shown to significant difference in birth weight.

Increased stillbirth rate have been reported, especially from areas where the epidemic has been present for a long time. The risk appears to be lower in asymptomatic women, although stillbirth rate more than double those in HIV sero-negative mothers, have been shown in some African centres. However some of the reported studies do not control for the presence of syphilis or other factors associated with stillbirth. A large study in Nairobi showed an independent association between HIV infection and both intra-uterine and intra-partum death, after controlling for the presence of other STDs [27].

Infection complication are also more common during the postpartum period in HIV-positive women. Caesarean section is particularly associated with higher infectious morbidity in some reports, is especially in women with low CD4+ counts, with an increased mortality.

3.5. Mother-To-Child Transmission

Reported rate of transmission of HIV from mother to child range from around 15%-25% in Europe and the USA to 25% to 40% in some African and Asia studies. With the advent of routine antiretroviral (ARV) therapy in many developed countries, much lower transmission rates are now being described [31]. The estimated annual incidence of perinatal infection declined by 27% in the united states between 1992 and 1995 after the widespread implementation of antiretroviral therapy in pregnancy.

Transmission of HIV-1 can occur in-utero, at the time of labour and delivery, or postnatally through breastfeeding. Knowledge about the likely timing of transmission is important for the design of possible interventions. Evidence for in-utero transmission (as early as 8 weeks gestation) comes from: the detection of HIV-1 in fetal specimen and placental tissue, viral isolation from 20%-60 of infected infants at the time of birth, the presence of p24 antigen in fetal serum; and an observed bimodal distribution of symptoms in children.

The evidence for intrapartum transmission came first from observation from a register of twins, which found that the first born twin had a two-fold higher risk of contracting HIV-1 than the second born twin. Exposure of the fetus to the virus in cervico-vaginal secretions is though to play a role, although the same phenomenon is observed for twin delivered by caesarean section. In addition, recent report have indicated that mode of delivery may affect the transmission rate.

Caesarean section whether elective or emergency has been shown to decrease transmission in some studies and prolonged reapture of membrane (more than four hours) to increase the risk of transmission. Around half of the infected infants will have negative viral studies at the time of birth. HIV has been shown in both the cell-free and cellular portions breast milk. Post-natal transmission through breastfeeding may explain the higher transmission rate seen in Africa.

The contribution each route to overall transmission has not been quantified exactly but it appears that in-utero transmission is less frequent and that a substantial proportion of infection occur at the time of delivery or late in pregnancy. This conclusion is based on the absence of an HIV-1 dysmorphic syndrome, the lack of manifestation of HIV-1 infection at birth and the finding that HIV-1 is detected in the first week of life in only about 50% of children later proven to be infected [6].

A working definition for the classification of the timing of transmission has been proposed, based on the time of detection of HIV in infant. Where virus is detectable within 48 hours of birth, an infant is considered to have been infected in utero, while intrapartum infection is assumed if viral studies are negative during the first week of life, but become positive between 7 and 90 days. A Markov model of the time to p24 antigenaemia based on results from the French collaborative study group suggested that 65% of infants were infected around the time of labour and 35% in utero. A probability of 27% for in utero transmission study (WITS) in the USA, while in Kinshasa, 23% of infants were though to be infected in utero, 65% intrapartum or early postpartum and 12% in late postpartum [32].

3.6. Factors Affecting Mother-To-Child Transmission Of HIV-1

Transmission from mother-to-child if HIV is affected by a number of factors, not all of which have been fully elucidated. These can be divided into viral, maternal, obstetrical, fetal and infant factors as demonstrated in Table 2.

4. Viral Factors

4.1. Viral load

Transmission is increased in the presence of high levels of material viraemia. Clinical observation of increased transmission in these situations, such as in advantage disease and at the time of seroconversion, are supported by the presence of high level of p24 antigenaemia. With the development of new technique for the measurement of the virus, such as quantitative polymerase chain reaction (PCR) DNA and RNA, an association has been shown between the material viral load and the risk of transmission from mother-to-child [34]. More than half of the women with viral load of >50 000 RNA copies per ml at the time of delivery have been shown to transmit the virus. A New York study showed a mean viral load 16000 RNA copies/ml in women in this study with measurable viral load were almost six times more likely to transmit than those in whom the was undetectable, after controlling for the CD4+ count. In a French study, transmission rates increased with increasing viral load: 12% in those with less than 1000 copies/ml compared with 29% in those with more than 10 000 copies/ml. Few studies have shown a threshold viral load for transmission and it appears that it can occur at low viral levels. For reasons which are not well understood, but which probably reflect the multiple influences acting on mother-to-child transmission.

The local viral load in cervico-vaginal secretion and in breast milk may also be an important determinant of transmission risk intrapartum and through HIV-1 levels in these fluid have been shown in most studies to be correlated with CD4+ count and plasma viral load. The presence of sexually transmitted diseased or other caused of inflammation, vitamin A deficiency and local immune respond may affect viral

Table 2: Regional estimate of people living with HIV/AIDS [33].

VIRAL	Viral genotype and phenotype Viral resistance Viral load
MATERIAL	Material immunological status Material nutritional status Material clinical status Behavioural factors Antiretroviral treatment
OBSTETRICAL	Prolonged rupture of membrane (>4 hours) Mode of delivery Intrapartum haemorrhage Obstetrical procedures Invasive fetal monitoring
FETAL	Prematurity Genetic Multiple pregnancy
INFANT	Breastfeeding Gastrointestinal track factors Immature immune system

shedding in Rwnada, postnatal transmission was associated with the presence of HIV-1 infected cell in breast milk [35].

Material antiretroviral therapy during pre-pregnancy is thought to reduce transmission partly through the reduction of viral load, although the mechanism may also include post-exposure prophylaxis in the child after birth, as the use of Zidovudine has been shown to reduce transmission at all levels of material viral load [6]. Combination antiretroviral therapy may be more effective in preventing transmission due to greater reductions in viral load but no large-scale study result are available yet on this.

4.2. Viral Genotype and Phenotype

A number of HIV-1 sub-type or clade group have been identified with differing geographical distributions. There is little evidence on the effect of sub-type on infection or transmission, although some studies have shown an increased in vitro ability of sub-type E to infect epithelial cells from the vaginal and cervix). The sub-type may affect the cell tropism of the virus, and in turn the infectivity, in-utero, through genital infection or in breast milk.

Most studies on viral variants in mothers and children have demonstrated that the strains in the infant are a distinct subset of maternal virus, although the major maternal variant has also been shown to be transmitted. Difference viral phenotype show differing tissue tropism. Macrophage tropic non-syncytium-inducing (NSI) viral isolates appear to be preferentially transmitted to children even when the dominant material strains are syncytium inducing (SI). There may be a difference in disease progression for the child related to the viral strain. Rapid/high virus isolate have been associated with non-transmitting mothers.

Increased strain diversity in the mother may theoretically influence the rate of transmission Repeated exposure to different viral strains through pregnancy, occurring through unprotected intercourse may be the mechanism responsible for the observed increase in transmission in these cases. The development of resistance zidvudine during pregnancy has been shown to be infrequent, but concern has been expressed that the possible development of resistant strain of HIV-1 in women receiving zidvudine monotherapy during pregnancy may result higher transmission rate in subsequent pregnancies. Whether the emergence of resistance is more likely with long course zidvudine compared with short course zidvudine is uncertain.

5. Maternal Factors

5.1. Maternal Immunological Status

Transmission from mother to child is more likely with decreased maternal immune status, reflected by low CD4+ counts, low CD4+ percentage or high CD4+ / CD8 ratio [5]. These in turn may be marker for higher viral loads as opposed to risk factors in themselves, although an interaction between viral load and immune response may be present. In the European collaborative study (ECS), there was be present. Risk of mother-to-child transmission where maternal CD4+ counts were below $700/mm^3$ (128). Transmission increased almost linearly in this study with decreasing CD4+ counts (166). Several other studies have noted similar associations.

In the WITS study, the association between low CD4+ percentages and transmission was only seen in women without persistently positive viral cultures, Where there was at least one negative culture and high CD4+ cell percentages, transmission rates were in the range of 1-4%. There have been conflicting results about the role of neutralizing antibodies in preventing transmission. Some studies have showed that high levels of material neutralizing antibody are associated with lower rate of transmission, while others showed no association. Women who transmit in-utero may have lower levels of autologous neutralizing antibody than those who do not transmit or those women where transmission occurs intrapartum.

Little is known about the role of mucosal HIV-1 antibodies and viral shedding in their genital track which may affect intrapartum transmission rates. Infection through breastfeeding has been associated with a lack of IgM and IgA in breast milk [35].

5.2. Maternal Nutritional Factors

Serum vitamin A levels in HIV-1 positive mothers have been correlated with the risk of transmission in a Malawi study. The mean vitamin A level in those mothers who transmitted virus to their children was significantly lower than in those who did not transmit. Women with vitamin A levels below 1.4 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ had a 4.4-fold increased risk of transmission, which dropped with increasing vitamin A levels. One US study no relationship between low vitamin A levels and transmission, while another cohort study did show a correlation. The mechanism of vitamin A effect is uncertain, but the influence of vitamin A on the integrity of the vaginal mucosa or placenta and the immune stimulatory properties of the vitamin have been suggested. Alternatively, low vitamin A levels may be marker for other deficiencies or behavioral factors, which influence transmission. Other micronutrient have been suggested as having a possible role, including zinc and Selenium.

5.3. Behavioural Factors

Several behavioral factors have been associated with an increased rate of transmission from mother-to-child. These include cigarette smoking and maternal hard use. Unprotected sexual intercourse during pregnancy has been linked to an increased risk of mother-to-child transmission. A transmission rate of 30% was shown in women who had more than 80 episodes of unprotected sex during pregnancy compared with 9.1% in those with no unprotected intercourse. A similar association is suggested in two African studies. This may be to an increased concentration or strain diversity of HIV-1 or the effect of cervical or vaginal inflammation or abrasions. An increase in chorioamnionitis has previously been reported linked to sexual activity in pregnancy, and this may be an alternative mechanism. The presence of sexually transmitted disease during pregnancy has been correlated with increased risk of transmission [36], and STDs have been shown to increase viral shedding in cervico-vaginal secretions.

5.4. Placental Factors

Placental factors have been implicated in transmission of the virus from mother-to-child. Placental infection with HIV-1 has been reported and Hofbauer cells and possibly trophoblasts express CD4+ and are thus susceptible to infection. Other placental infections and non-infectious condition such as abruption placenta have also been implicated. Breaks in the placental surface can occur at any stage of pregnancy and may be related to transmission, although the significance of these may, in turn, depend upon the maternal viral load. Smoking and drug use, both associated with increased transmission, may exert this effect through placental disruption. In area of high malaria prevalence, is common in pregnancy. Placental *P. falciparum* infestation has been associated with poorer survival in infants born to HIV-1 positive mothers in Malawi, which may represent increased transmission rates and with higher rates of transmission from mother-to-child in Kenya.

5.5. Obstetric Factors

With the majority of mother-to-child transmission occurring at the time of labour and delivery, obstetric factors are important determinants of transmission. Suggested mechanisms for intrapartum transmission of HIV-1 include direct skin and mucous membrane contact between the infant and maternal cervico-vaginal secretions during labour, ingestion of virus from these secretions, and ascending infection to the amniotic fluid. HIV-1 in cervico-vaginal secretions may be raised four-fold during pregnancy. The higher rate of infection in first-born twins may be due to longer exposure of the infant to infected secretions. Several obstetric factors have been implicated, although result are not consistent across studies with regard to the relative importance of different obstetric factors. In the French perinatal Cohort study, preterm delivery, intrapartum haemorrhage and obstetric procedure were related to transmission risk [36]. Other factors such as the use of fetus scalp electrodes, episiotomy, vaginal tears and operative delivery have been implicated in some studies but not in other. The duration of labour does not appear to be as important as duration of rupture of membranes prolonged rupture of membrane has been associated with increased risk of transmission in a number of studies and is an important risk factor in an American study, duration of ruptured membranes of over four hours nearly double the risk of infection, regardless of the eventual mode of delivery. Delivery by caesarean section has been shown to be protective in some prospective follow-up studies, but not in all. A randomized controlled trial is in progress in Europe. This has now confirmed by a. A Swiss study showed an additive protective effective caesarean section for women receiving antiretroviral treatment. In France women who received long-course antiretroviral treatment in pregnancy and had an elective caesarean section had a transmission rate of less than 1%.

5.6. Fetal Factors

Fetal genetic factors may play a part in transmission. Little is known yet about the role of genetic factors such as the CCR-5 delta 32 deletion and HLA compatibility of mother and infant in the determination of transmission risk concordance between infant and maternal HLA has been associated with increased risk of transmission [37].

Preterm infant have higher reported rate of transmission of HIV-1 in several studies [6]. Women with low CD4+ counts are more likely to have preterm deliveries, which may influence this finding. The higher rate of infection seen in first-born twins have been widely reported and have formed part of the evidence for the role of intrapartum transmission. This effect is more pronounced in vaginally delivery twins, where a two fold increase in infection is seen in first born twins than second born, but is also present in twin delivered by caesarean section. Other fetal factors may include co-infection with other pathogens, fetal nutrition and fetal immune status.

5.7. Infant Factors

Breastfeeding is responsible for a high proportion of mother-to-child transmission in developing countries, where 30% or more of perinatal HIV infection will occur through breast milk. This is less common in the developed world, where most HIV-positive women will not breast feed. Breast milk contain both cell associated and free virus, the amount of which may be related to the immune suppression of the mother and vitamin A levels. Other protective factors are also present in breast milk, including mucins, HIV antibodies, lactoferrin, and secretory leukocyte protease inhibitor (SLPI) [6].

A meta-analysis of studies of transmission through breastfeeding showed the additional risk of transmission through breastfeeding to be

between 7 and 22%, equivalent to a double of transmission rates. A Soweto study has shown transmission rates of 18% in formula fed infants compared with 42% in breastfed. Rates are higher when the mother sero-converts during breastfeeding, where the estimated risk is around 30%. The risk of breast milk transmission may also depend upon other factors, such as maternal disease stage, breast abscesses, mastitis, nipple cracks, maternal Vitamin A and oral thrush in the child. A Zimbabwe study showed that 31% of breastfeeding mothers of HIV-1 infected children had active nipple disease.

Late postnatal transmission, after the age of six months has been described in a number of studies [6]. In Abidjan, 12% of infant born to HIV-1 positive mother were diagnosed after the age of six months but may have been infected earlier.

The risk of postnatal transmission may also be other factors in the newborn. HIV entry may occur through the gastro-intestinal tract following ingestion of virus in utero or at birth. There is decreased acidity, decreased mucus, lower IgA activity and thinned mucosa in the newborn gastro-intestinal tract, which may facilitate transmission [6]. The newborn immune system may also be deficient in macrophage and T cell immune response. Increasing the susceptibility to infection. At least part of the effect of antiretroviral drugs in pregnancy appear to be due to a post exposure prophylaxis effect after birth.

6. Interventions to Prevent Mother-to-Child Transmission of HIV

With increasing knowledge about the underlying mechanism of mother-to-child transmission of HIV-1 has come an increased emphasis on the search for interventions to prevent or reduce the risk of transmission [6]. The successful use of antiretroviral therapy in developed countries has led to suggestion that it may eventually be possible to reduce prenatal transmission rate to less than 2%. A number of possible intervention strategies have been proposed or are under investigation.

6.1. Possible Strategies Known For The Prevention Of Mother-To-Child Transmission Of HIV Termination of pregnancy

Behavioural interventions

- Reduction in the frequency of unprotected sexual intercourse during pregnancy
- Reduction in the number of sexual partners during pregnancy
- Lifestyle change, including avoidance of drug use and smoking in pregnancy
- Therapeutic interventions
- Antiretroviral therapy: Zidovudine alone or combination, long or short-course
- Vitamin A and other micronutrients
- Immunotherapy
- Treatment of STD
- Obstetric interventions
- Avoidance of invasive tests
- Birth canal cleansing
- Caesarean section delivery
- Modification of infant feeding practice
- Avoidance of breastfeeding
- Early cessation of breastfeeding

According to Kuhn and Stein, preventing new infections in women who are fertile is still crucial. This entails lowering women's susceptibility to HIV-1 infection by elevating their social standing, educating people about HIV/AIDS and how to prevent it, encouraging safer sexual behaviour, including the use of barrier techniques, and providing appropriate treatment for STDs [3, 4]. Access to proper contraception and information to help them determine their future fertility should be provided to women who are known to be HIV positive.

Access to termination of pregnancy for HIV positive women can also reduce the burden of paediatric AIDS cases, but should be viewed as an option for individual women, rather than a public health intervention for the prevention of transmission. Most women living with HIV will decide to continue with pregnancy, even where termination is offered.

Currently, zidovudine (either as long-course through pregnancy, labour, and six weeks to the infant, or as short-course) and refraining from breastfeeding are the only interventions that have been shown to be effective in reducing mother-to-child transmission (MTCT) of HIV. Numerous other options are still being researched, with a particular emphasis on treatments that take place during labour and delivery, as this is when it is thought that most transmissions take place. A vitamin A study conducted in Malawi is among the completed studies that are currently undergoing analysis.

Studies on formula feeding that were randomised and carried out in Nairobi, as well as a self-selection study that examined how breastfeeding affected transmission in Soweto. There are still research being conducted on the effects of short-course antiretrovirals, vaginal decontamination (in Kenya), and vitamin A supplementation (in South Africa, Zimbabwe, and Tanzania). There hasn't been any research done on postpartum interventions other than formula feeding.

7. Intervention to Reduce Mother-to-Child Transmission

The ideal intervention for the reduction of mother-to-child transmission would be one that is widely applicable in resource poor settings [38]. Vaginal disinfection and vitamin A administration would not require identification of HIV positive women. The minimum requirements for the implementation of other interventions in health services include:

- Access to and use of appropriate antenatal, intrapartum and postpartum care with adequately trained health workers,
- Adequate pre and post test counselling services.
- Ability to afford the cost of reliable HIV testing
- Appropriate laboratory facilities to monitor blood parameters during therapy
- Delivery units with access to disinfectants, gloves and clean needles

- Acceptance and uptake of the intervention by HIV infected women
- A regimen that is logistically possible to implement in term of dosing times and routes, drug storage and distribution
- A regimen which is affordable for the health service.

7.1. Antiretroviral Therapy

Long-Course Zidovudine Treatment

One significant development in the prevention of HIV-1 transmission from mother to child has been the outcome of the paediatric AIDS clinical trials group (PACTG) study PACTG076, which tested the use of zidovudine (ZDV) in pregnancy in asymptomatic women. It has been demonstrated that administering zidovudine orally after 14 weeks of pregnancy, intravenously during labour, and to the newborn for six weeks in a non-breastfed community significantly reduces mother-to-child HIV-1 transmission. In many industrialised nations, this is now the norm for prenatal care, and reported transmission rates have decreased as a result [6].

In this randomized placebo-controlled trial conducted in the USA and France, in a non-breastfeeding population, treatment with ZDV (100mg 5 times daily) or placebo was started between 14-34 weeks of pregnancy (median 26 weeks). Women also received intravenous ZDV or placebo during labour and the infants received oral ZDV (2mg/kg 4 times daily) or placebo for six weeks. All women had CD4+counts >200 per mm^3 , were symptom free and not previously received ZDV. The first interim analysis on 356 mother-infant pairs demonstrated a rate of mother-to-child transmission of 25.5% in the placebo group, and 8.3% in the ZDV group. Treatment with ZDV achieved a 67.5% reduction in transmission risk. The drug was well tolerated in the short-term in the pregnant women and the neonates.

The effect of ZDV in reducing transmission appear to be partly through the reduction of material viral load, although transmission occurred at a wide range of viral load in the PACTG076 study. An additional level of protection through post exposure prophylaxis in the infant is also hypothesized, as ZDV readily crosses the placenta [6].

Further evidence for a post-exposure effect come from a retrospective new york state study of the efficacy of abbreviated zidovudine regimens. Women who received ZDV from the prenatal period had a transmission rate of 6.1%. when treatment was commenced intrapartum, transmission was 10%, when starts within 48 hours of birth 9.3% and when started on day 3 or later, transmission was 18.4%.

A follow-up research among the uninfected infants born to women participating in ACTG076 has provided assurance that in-utero exposure to zidovudine does not appear to generate any unforeseen long-term effects. The follow-up data from 112 uninfected children in the placebo group and 122 uninfected children in the zidovudine group are reported in this study. At the time of the most recent follow-up, the children ranged in age from 3.2 to 5.6 years, with a median of 4.2 years.

No difference could be detected in any parameter of growth, cognitive and development function assessed by the Bailey Scale of infant development immunology function cardiac function or orphthalmologic function in addition there were no late deaths and no malignancies detected in this group.

The use of long-course ZDV in pregnancy is recommended as the standard of care in the united state, Europe and in some other countries, including Thailand and Brazil. The introduction of this policy has led to a dramatic reduction in the reported transmission rate in the united state and France. Transmission rate in Los Angeles have dropped from 30% to 10%, in North Carilina form 21% to 8.5%. In France, a two-third reduction in transmission [form 14% to 5%] has been report. However, the of the intervention depend upon the access of HIV positive women to therapy. In area where utilization of antenatal care is low. And thus access to counseling, testing and drugs provision is reduced, the efficacy will be lower. This has been shown in the Bronx, New york, where only 40% of HIV-infected women were identified before birth and less than half of these received ZDV.

The use of ZDV in this regimen is not directly application to the majority of women in the developing world where the majority of mother-to-child transmission occurs. This is because of the high cost of the intervention (in the USA the regimen cost over US\$ 1000 per mother-child pair); the logistic of monitoring of blood parameter drug reactions; intravenous infusion during delivery and treatment to the newborn for six weeks. In addition, the intervention needs to be introduced early on in pregnancy, when most women in resource-poor setting only attend antenatal care late in pregnancy. Lack of access to pregnancy. Lack of access to counseling and testing in these settings limits the use of antiretroviral in pregnancy. Women in developing countries have higher rate of aneamia, which may be exacerbated by antiretroviral treatment, and may differ in diseased status from those in developed countries.

The PACTG076 trial was conducted in a non-breastfeeding population, and the efficacy of the regimen in a breastfeeding population need to be determined, as any reduction in transmission prior to or during labour may be negated by an increased transmission from breast milk. The acceptability of these intervention in developing countries will require further study.

Some resistant strains of virus have been report ZDV treatment to prevent transmission. Although resistance appear to be uncommon, there has been concern about the use of ZDV monotherapy in the management in any subsequent pregnancy.

There is now no proof of teratogenicity or short-term negative effects on the foetus or infant, according to the results of the PACTG076 study and the ZDV in pregnancy registry. Furthermore, follow-up of uninfected infants exposed to zidovudine in utero until age four has not shown any medium-term deleterious effect. To find out whether an uncommon but serious adverse effect might develop, a bigger group of children needs to be observed for a longer period of time and follow-up is still necessary. It is still need to conduct longer-term follow-up found that ZDV was harmful to mice, have grown more concerned about the medications' long-term effects. The national institute for health and care in 1997 convened a consensus group, which recommended against changing the recommendation for ZDV usage during pregnancy due to insufficient data. Pregnant women who expose their children to ZDV should keep an eye out for any long-term harmful effects.

It has been suggested that ZDV use in pregnancy would be a cost effective intervention in both developed and developing countries, if implementation problems can be overcome . The use of shorter course regimens or other antiretroviral drugs provides a feasible alternative.

7.2. Short-Course Zidovudine Therapy

Shorter drug regimens in pregnancy would be more feasible in resource-poor settings. Results from from some developed country studies suggest that antenatal oral ZDV alone may be as effective as antenatal, intrapartum and postpartum regimens. To date three randomized trials of short course therapy have been published from resource-poor setting.

A trial of short-course zidovudine treatment in Thailand has shown a significant effect in preventing transmission [39].

The Bangkok perinatal AZT study, was a randomized placebo-controlled trial to evaluate the safety and efficacy of a short-course of oral zidovudine [ZDV] administered during late pregnancy and labour to reduce the risk for perinatal HIV transmission. The regimen was 300mg ZDV orally twice daily from 36 weeks gestation until the delivery. All women were advised not to breastfeed and were provided with infant formula, and it is important to bear in mind that these results are directly applicable only to formula-fed infants [39].

A trial conducted in 260 women in Côte d'Ivoire randomized women to receive either oral zidovudine 300 mg twice a day from 36 weeks until the onset of labour or matching placebo.

At the onset of labour zidovudine 300mg was given every three hours until delivery versus placebo. In this trial population over 95% of the infants were breastfed by their mothers and by three months of age 19 out of 115 babies in the zidovudine group were HIV infected compared with 30 out of 115 in the placebo group. This represents a relative risk of transmission of 0.63 (95% confidence intervals 0.38-1.06). The transmission risk at three months was similar to the transmission risk seen at four weeks also suggesting that breastfeeding had not produced a substantial narrowing of the difference between the two groups.

These results demonstrate that short-course oral zidovudine appears to be safe and effective at reducing the risk of mother-to-infant HIV transmission if started at the time of delivery and then given to the mother postnatal. The dose does not seem to produce a substantial difference in the size of the treatment effect. Of importance for many developing countries is that whether the women do or do not breastfeed does not appear to make a substantial difference to the effectiveness of treatment [38].

7.3. Combination Therapy and Other Antiretroviral Drugs

In addition to the usual ACTG076 zidovudine regimen, a recent French study described the use of 3TC (lamivudine) starting at 32 weeks gestation. The data was only given in abstract form. The babies were given both medications until they were six weeks old. A cohort of 899 women receiving zidovudine alone was compared with 200 women receiving this combination. In the combination group, the rate of transmission was 2.6%, while in the zidovudine group, it was 6.5%. The lower chance of transmission could be explained by other factors, given this study was not a randomised trial.

One discovery, though, was that two newborns in the 3TC group who were not infected passed away from a neurological condition brought on by a mitochondrial myopathy. Given the rarity of this illness and the two infant deaths in 200 women, 3TC may be to blame.

Although it hasn't been fully publicised, a randomised trial with zidovudine and 3TC in South Africa has also been completed. This study examined the efficacy of three distinct medication regimens in comparison to a placebo. Arm B was given 3TC and zidovudine from a 36-week-old infant. gestation to the mother and child during labour and for a week following delivery. Arm B was given a child and zidovudine. Zidovudine and 3TC were only given to the arm during labour. In total, more than 1300 women were enlisted. By the time the research population is six weeks old, the majority of the women are breastfeeding, and the risk of transmission in Arm A was 8.6%, Arm B was 10.8%, Arm C was 17.7%, and in the placebo group it was 17.2%. The study population is still being monitored.

Another strategy for preventing perinatal transmission is the use of non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTI). Nevirapine is an NNRTI with strong antiretroviral activity and a good safety record, however the medicine's duration of action is limited by the quick emergence of drug resistance. The drug's ability to reach high, long-lasting levels is especially intriguing because it opens the door to the potential of treating labourers with only one dose. An efficacy trial is scheduled for the near future, and preliminary research are already underway.

With more significant viral load decreases, combined antiretroviral therapy is being used more frequently. According to recent guidelines for HIV medication therapy, patients should take at least two drugs, with the possibility of adding a protease inhibitor. Although such recommendations are subject to frequent changes due to the rapid advancements in HIV medicine, patients undergoing this level of care may have undetectable viral levels. Most of these medications have not been used in pregnancy before, and the long-term effects on the foetuses of many of the most recent antiretroviral (ARV) medications have not been thoroughly studied.

Phase I trials are completed or in progress for nevirapine, stavudine, didanosine, lamivudine, MKC-442 and the protease inhibitor [6]. DMP-266 (Efavirenz, Sustiva) was shown to cause moderate to serious birth defects in monkeys, and may not be suitable for use in early pregnancy.

7.4. Immune Therapy

Alternative methods of preventing HIV transmission to children have included both active immunisation with the vaccine and passive immunisation with hyper-immune HIV immunoglobulin (HIVIG) [31]. Intravenous HIV immunoglobulin as a passive immunisation has been studied. A low transmission rate was seen in both the study and control group of the HIVIG trial [ACTG185], which had a cohort of women who had all taken ZDV. As a result, the study was discontinued. The transmission risk for HIVIG was 6.0% (9.5% confidence interval 2.8%-9.1%) and 4.1% (95% confidence interval 1.5%-6.7%) for the HIVIG Group.

It would have taken a very large sample size to demonstrate any discernible drop in these rates linked to the use of HIVIG. Concerns about the price and source of donor for these goods, uniform preparation, and the best delivery time are still present despite the fact that another trial on ZDV naïve products is being conducted in Uganda. Through the passive transfer of antibodies, active immunisation may be able to induce immunity in both the mother and the foetus [6]. Although multiple phase I/II trials are ongoing, an effective vaccination has not yet been discovered.

7.5. Nutritional Interventions

Supplementing with vitamin A has been recommended as a preventive measure in response to the discovery that mothers who had low serum levels of the vitamin were more likely to pass HIV to their offspring [40]. There are numerous ongoing randomised controlled trials including vitamin A and other micronutrients. Micronutrient supplementation has several potential benefits, including low cost, potential additional nutritional and health benefits for the mother, and ease of implementation without HIV testing.

Increases in the viral load in breast milk have also been linked to vitamin A insufficiency; hence, any decrease in this load after supplementation would likewise be advantageous for nursing mothers. Other micronutrients that have also been proposed as potential

preventative agents include zinc and selenium.

Multivitamin supplementation reduced the risk of low birth weight by 44%, severe preterm birth (under 34 weeks gestation) by 39%, and small size for gestation age at birth by 43% in HIV-positive pregnant women, according to a randomised controlled trial conducted in Tanzania. Vitamin A supplementation had no effect on these variables. The multivitamin intake led to significant increases in CD4+, CD8, and CD3 counts, but not in vitamin A levels. The study's impact on mother-to-child transmission is yet unknown. Supplementing with vitamin A alone does not appear to have much of an impact on transmission, according to preliminary data from other vitamin A intervention trials.

7.6. Mode of Delivery

A decrease in transmission has been linked to caesarean section delivery in certain studies, but not in all of them. Despite the absence of solid data at the time, caesarean sections have become the standard birth method for HIV-positive women in several places. 44% of mothers in the UK who tested positive for HIV had caesarean sections in 1995.

A 1994 meta-analysis of prospective follow-up studies revealed that caesarean sections slightly decreased the risk of transmission. After controlling for antiretroviral medication, birth weight, and maternal illness stage, elective caesarean sections decreased the incidence of MTCT by more than 50% in a more recent meta-analysis that included five prospective trials from Europe and ten from North America, totalling over 8500 mother-infant pairings. According to a French trial, women who underwent an elective caesarean section and got long-term antiretroviral medication had a transmission rate of 0.8%, as opposed to 6.6% for vaginal delivery. According to a Swiss study (Kind et al., 1998), 45% of women who had an elective caesarean section and long-course ZDV showed no signs of transmission. Europe has conducted a form of administration randomised controlled experiment.

This trial randomized in excess of 400 women to elective caesarean section delivery or expectation of vaginal delivery. There out of 170 infant (1.8%) born to women in the caesarean section group were HIV infected compared with 21 out of 200 (10.5%) born to women in the vaginal group. A treatment effect odds ratio of 0.2 (95% confidence interval 0.1-0.6). Pregnant women who participated in the trial were exposed to zidovudine in two thirds of cases. In this subgroup, kids born to mothers scheduled for caesarean sections had an HIV infection rate of 0.8%, while babies born to women scheduled for vaginal deliveries had an HIV infection rate of 4.3%. This results in an odds ratio of 0.2 for women who were not exposed to zidovudine during pregnancy, with 95% confidence intervals ranging from 0-1.7. The odds ratio for transmission was likewise 0.2, indicating that the prophylactic effect of caesarean sections holds true regardless of whether women were prescribed zidovudine during pregnancy or not.

Furthermore, neither group experienced any significant unfavourable effects. The prevalence of postpartum fever was generally modest, but it was more frequently observed in women who had caesarean sections. When deciding whether to perform a caesarean section, doctors must consider the following factors: the likelihood of maternal morbidity and death; the accessibility of maternity services for women planning future pregnancies; the availability of safe operating facilities; and the potential for increased service commitment.

7.7. Vaginal Cleansing

One potential strategy to decrease HIV-1 intrapartum transmission has been suggested: using antiseptics or antiviral agents to clear the birth canal during labour and delivery. Studies conducted in Scandinavia have shown that group B streptococci can be reduced in transmission by using chlorhexidine lavage. The idea is appealing for HIV prevention since it would be a low-cost intervention that is easily implemented in the majority of healthcare settings, it wouldn't require women to be identified as HIV positive before the intervention, and it might have other health advantages.

In a quasi-randomised research conducted in Malawi, babies were given a chlorhexidine wash and a four-hourly aqueous chlorhexidine 0.25% solution by vaginal swabbing following vaginal examination. A control group did not receive any wash. The study group's rate of HIV transmission did not decrease overall, but only 60% of the infants were monitored. Mothers whose membranes had ruptured for longer than four hours saw a significant decrease in transmission. In this trial, the majority of deliveries took place shortly after the vaginal swabbing technique. Following this management, there were also notable decreases in newborn and puerperal sepsis. In addition to any potential benefit in preventing HIV MTCT, using this treatment might be beneficial for these additional health benefit. To optimise the potential benefit, benalkonium chloride has been proposed as an alternate antiseptic agent for vaginal lavage, using the antiseptic form 36 week gestation. In resource-poor situations, vaginal cleansing intervention is still a viable alternative. To find out if the efficacy may be increased, more study should be done on various agent formulations and concentrations, as well as application techniques.

7.8. Modification of Infant Feeding Practice

It is commonly known that breastfeeding increases the risk of HIV transmission. In underdeveloped nations, where 1 in 7 children born to HIV-positive mothers will become infected through breast milk, breastfeeding accounts for a significant share of mother-to-child transmission. The rate of transmission could be doubled by breastfeeding [6]. It could also be the primary factor influencing the variation in the rate of transmission between industrialised and developing nations. According to a meta-analysis of studies on breastfeeding-related transmission, the additional risk of transmission through breastfeeding is almost 30% for women who get sick during the nursing phase and ranges from 7 to 22% overall. Complete avoidance of breastfeeding, early weaning, pasteurisation of breast milk, and refraining from nursing in the event of a breast abscess or damaged nipple are some potential modifications to newborn feeding practices [6].

While there is a need for more research into the relationship between HIV infection nutritional status and immune function in breastfeeding mothers, the discussion of appropriate infant feeding has almost entirely focused on the risks and benefits of breastfeeding for the infant. Maternal considerations should also be taken into note. The possible consequences of nursing and subsequent weight loss on the mother's immunity and long-term prognosis are among the factors raising concerns regarding the impact of breastfeeding on maternal health in HIV-positive women. It is also necessary to take into account the impact of severe immunosuppression or malnourishment on the function of the immunologically active component of breast milk and the danger of transmission in breast milk [41]. If it were possible to detect infants who were already HIV positive at birth, breast milk might be beneficial for them

Few HIV-positive mothers will breastfeed in wealthy nations (Italian Register for HIV, 1994). For financial, practical, and cultural reasons, an alternative to nursing might not be possible in resource-poor situations. The mother should be taught about the benefits and risks of breastfeeding in relation to HIV infection and be encouraged to make an educated choice regarding nursing her child. It is important to encourage them in their choice [4]. When a mother tests positive for HIV, it is important to provide her with an acceptable means of alternate feeding.

8. Conclusion

This review expresses the importance of improving local health systems and prioritizing resources to search for effective interventions to prevent the prevalence of HIV infection on infants from HIV-infected mothers. This research is critical to reducing the global burden of mother-to-child transmission of HIV and creating health equality for all.

Significance statement: The prevalence of HIV infection in infants born to HIV-infected mothers is a pressing global health issue. The World Health Organization estimates that in 2018, 570,000 children under age 15 were newly infected with HIV, and the majority of those infections were attributed to mother to child transmission of the virus. HIV infection in infants born to HIV-infected mothers can have devastating and long-lasting effects on an affected child's health as well as their psychological, social, and economic wellbeing. This paper reviewed the current scientific literature examining the prevalence of HIV infection on infants from HIV-infected mothers.

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